

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Continental Region in Germany

PROBLEM

What are the most popular and effective agroecological methods for weed control in the Continental Region in Germany?

STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

All stakeholders agreed on inter-row tillage, mechanical tillage, crop rotation, high seed rates and mulching. A significant group of stakeholders were familiar with other methods such as manual weed control (80%), certified seeds (80%), cover crops and mowing pastures (80%). Mechanical tillage was also the most frequently used method reported by farmers (50%), followed by crop rotation and certified seeds, each used by 40% of respondents. Other methods, such as tillage between rows, mixed cropping, increased seed rates, and cover crops are utilized by only 10% of farmers. Methods like weed mapping and flaming, narrow rows, sowing timing and ground covers are less common due to lower awareness and high costs.

Figure 1: winter barley experimental plant

RECOMMENDATION

Emphasize the use of mechanical tillage, crop rotation, and certified seeds as primary strategies for weed control. Encourage the adoption of mulch and no-till seeding to improve soil health and weed management. Promote financial incentives for high-cost methods like flaming, especially in specialized crops. Increase awareness and training on lesser-known methods such as weed mapping and cover crops to enhance overall effectiveness in weed control.

Figure 2: Broad sowing with weed treatment

Figure 3: Single weed with treatment

KEYWORDS

agroecological methods for weed control, mechanical tillage, crop rotation, seed rate, sowing time, certified seed, catch crop, mulching, flaming, weed mapping, under sowing, mulch sowing, direct sowing, soil health

AUTHORSHIP

Bürgener, U., ASS, Saxony, Germany

